

AfriPlantSci

Healthy Plants, Healthy People, Healthy Planet

Summary Report

The AfriPlantSci summer school of 2019 was aimed at African early career researchers facing African plant health challenges. Feedback from the participants has shown that the training was targeted and relevant to the skills gap of African early career researchers working in plant health. The course built the technical capacity, core skills capacity and the scientific confidence of the participants. The summer school also developed new scientific networks and, in the short time since the course, has already led to collaborative funding submissions, with more planned in the next year. JIC staff and students increased their understanding of African agricultural and research challenges through the interactions they experienced on the workshop. The activities of JIC and ACACIA were showcased through social media and website articles during the workshop. The AfriPlantSci 2019 summer school was recognised as a success by all contributors; participants, trainers, PIPS students and Pwani University.

23
course participants

622 applications

11
African countries

Representing
14 institutions

Introduction

It is increasingly recognised that addressing global plant health challenges is critical for achieving the sustainable development goals for 2030. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) estimates that insect pests are damaging up to 40 percent of food crops globally. And in terms of global economic impact, FAO estimates that plant diseases cost around \$220 billion and invasive insects around \$70 billion. To highlight this challenge, the UN has proclaimed 2020 the International Year of Plant Health to boost funding and understanding. There is real need for research and for innovative solutions to these challenges faced globally. In this context, the AfriPlantSci course provided a very timely contribution

This second AfriPlantSci course was the result of a collaboration between Pwani University (PU) and the John Innes Centre (JIC) under the umbrella of the Alliance for Accelerated Crop Improvement in Africa (ACACIA) of which JIC and the Biosciences East and Central Africa – International Livestock Research Institute (BecA-ILRI) are co-founders.

The course was hosted at PU in Kilifi, Kenya and was jointly co-ordinated by a team of organisers from PU and JIC. Much of the training was led by JIC faculty, post-docs and technical staff with additional trainers from PU, African Women in Agricultural Research and Development (AWARD) and the University of Nottingham. In addition, six PhD students from the Norwich Research Park Doctoral training programme (NRP DTP) contributed towards the workshop through various activities as part of their Professional Internship for PhD Students (PIPS) placements. This second edition of AfriPlantSci provided a rich learning and collaborative environment for all the participants, organisers and trainers to interact.

The course covered a broad range of science related to plant health (Appendix A), with faculty focusing on recent results combined with practical hands-on experience of the latest techniques to advance research in this area. The topics covered were:

- Evolutionary genomics and plant abiotic stresses
- Plant transformation and gene editing
- Bioinformatics for field pathogenomics
- Insect mediated plant disease.

To support the technical aspects of the course there were also series of workshops to provide the participants with the necessary core skills to advance their research careers. The workshops covered the following skills:

- Making a career plan
- Formulating scientific questions and crafting proposals
- Speaking with impact
- Gender responsive research
- Research ethics
- Manuscript writing
- Researcher job applications

The course was advertised to African early career researchers which included MSc and PhD students and researchers within last five years of their PhD. A total of 622 applications were received for 15 open places, one place was reserved for an AWARD fellow from Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR), six places were awarded to PU staff and one place was awarded to a member of staff from the Kenyan National Biosafety Authority (NBA), giving a total of 23 participant places. The participants came from twelve institutes across ten countries. For further details see Appendix B.

Aims of the course

1. To build capacity and capability among the next generation of African plant scientists;
2. To forge future partnerships between UK and African partners;
3. To increase understanding among UK staff and students of the challenges in African agricultural science;
4. To showcase ACACIA's activity in Africa, thereby increasing the success of future capacity building.

The remainder of this report will detail the inputs, outputs and outcomes under each one of these aims.

Building capacity and capability among the next generation of African plant scientists

The participants were asked to complete a survey before the course and then again 4 weeks after the course to determine the immediate impact that the course. The questions for the surveys were designed around a measurement framework and theory of change that were developed for the course and can be found in Appendix C.

Participants were asked to rate their general confidence in different areas before and after the workshop (Fig. 1). In general, the participants had some considerable confidence in the areas we were targeting before the course. This is not surprising given the stringency of the application process. However, despite this confidence before the course, the average perceived confidence of the participants did increase further after the course.

"I applied everything that Peter said into my workshop presentation. I got enormously positive feedback from everybody on my story. It boosted my confidence. Brande and Cristobal interviewed me and I was completely terrified and nervous. I did it anyway and I got constructive feedback and I feel that if I could go through that interview then I'm certainly going to ace all my future interviews."

- Edith Mugehu (Zimbabwe Sugar Association Experiment Station)

Capacity

The participants were asked the level of skill that they feel like they currently have before and after the workshop. This perceived level is summarised in Fig. 2 and on average across all technical skills the score before changed from 1.9 to 3.5. Across all core skills the participants at the beginning of the workshop felt that they had a fairly high skill in each area averaging 2.9 and still afterwards they felt that their skill level was higher after the workshop averaging 3.5.

Figure 2 Average Perceived skill level of participants in technical skills (a) and core skills (b). The participants were asked to score each skill as the level they currently have, 1 = very low and 5 = very high before the workshop and four weeks after the workshop.

Figure 1. Average confidence scores before and after the workshop. 1 = very low confidence, 5 = very high confidence. The scores were averaged across all participants for the three area indicated in the key.

Self-assessed skill scoring increased:

(From anonymously submitted surveys)

84.2%
for technical skills

20.7%
for core skills

It was important that this course provided applicable training and skills for the participants. To make sure that the course content was relevant we asked the participants to score from 1-5 their need for training with one being very low and five being very high. To check if any of the skills were immediately applied to their work we also assessed how frequently the participants had used the skills four weeks after the workshop using the same scoring system.

For technical skills (fig. 3), 60% or more participants indicated they had a high need for training in all the technical skills apart from 'using a micropipette' (45%). Following the course, general molecular biology skills were utilised frequently by about 40% participants and specific technical skills were used frequently by between 10-30% participants. The seemingly low application of these skills at a group level will be based on the participants individual needs for their specific research projects.

Figure 3. Technical skills: the percentage of participants that scored the need for training as high and have since frequently used the skill. The participants were asked to score the need for training before the workshop out of five with 1 = very low and 5 = very high. Participants were subsequently asked to score how frequently they used the skill four weeks after the workshop with 1 = very low and 5 = very high. The Y axis shows the percentage of participants that scored need for training or frequency of use at 4 or 5.

For core skills (fig. 4), More than 85% of participants indicated a high need for training for all the core skills training modules. And even more impressive is that since the workshop more than 50% of the participants suggest that they have frequently used 5/7 of the skills. This is demonstrating a large skill gap that many early career researchers face and that this course successfully addressed.

"I have applied the skills of Manuscript writing that Cristobal took us through and have come up with a better Manuscript for publication. Being introduced to BioXIV for publication of my negative results was a great opportunity that I am going to seize."

-David Livingston Nsibo (University of Pretoria)

Figure 4. Core skills: the percentage of participants that scored the need for training as high and have since frequently used the skill. The participants were asked to score the need for training before the workshop out of five with 1 = very low and 5 = very high. Participants were subsequently asked to score how frequently they used the skill four weeks after the workshop with 1 = very low and 5 = very high. The Y axis shows the percentage of participants that scored need for training or frequency of use at 4 or 5.

It was hoped that the impact of the workshop training would be amplified through the participants transferring the skills that they learnt back to colleagues at their home institutions. Four weeks after the course 81% of participants surveyed said they had passed on skills learnt at the summer school to others at their home institutions.

"Practical sessions both bioinformatics and laboratory were a great breakthrough and I learnt many basic skills and best practices that are transferable to my colleagues"

- Florence Munguti (KEPHIS)

81%

Participants reported to have passed on skills learnt at the summer school (after 4 weeks).

87.5%

Participants reported to feel they had gained new contacts for future collaboration.

84.6%

Trainers reported to feel they had gained new contacts for future collaboration.

To forge future partnerships between UK and African partners

All participants surveyed post workshop said they gained either many (87.5%) or a few (12.5%) new contacts that they would be open to future collaboration with. And mirroring this, 84.6% of trainers surveyed (including PIPS students) said they gained valuable new connections to African focused researchers and 76.9% gained valuable new connections to African research institutions.

These connections can be formalised through funding applications and impressively more than 50% of participants (62.6%) and trainers (53.9%) expect to submit applications for funding with contacts made during the workshop within the next year. Just two months after the beginning of the workshop two funding proposals had already been submitted. James Canham (JIC PIPS student) with collaborators at the Kenyan Plant Health Inspectorate Service (KEPHIS), Pwani University and The Kenyan Medical Research Institute (KEMRI-Wellcome Trust) and Cambridge University were successful in securing funding through OpenPlant to address Coconut Lethal Yellow Disease in Kenya.

One contributing factor to the success of forging partnerships was the hard work of the six PIPS students facilitating the course. Each PIPS student had their individual roles and contributed enthusiastically throughout the workshop. Many of the participants appreciated the PIPS knowledge, enthusiasm and helpfulness in their feedback.

"I must say the PIPs were so open and helpful and I thank them for that. The main scientists were all so willing to help even after the course... I have also learnt from the participants and identified those I can work with in future"

- Virginia Gichuru (Pwani University)

"[The PIPS students] were very open, I learnt from each one of them and they have positively impacted my life. During the different practicals they assisted me, always ready to answer my questions and help me to seek clearance from the scientists whenever needed. They have also shared with me their experiences"

- Frejus Sodedji (University of Abomey-calavi)

To increase understanding among JIC staff and students of the challenges in African agriculture

76.9% trainers surveyed (including PIPS) said that they improved/gained greater understanding of African research topics and challenges due to the workshop. When asked how their knowledge of African research has changed the trainers and PIPS said they had increased their knowledge in: species of regional importance, societal and cultural impacts, capacity of institutes to conduct research, and the applied focus of African research especially towards farmers.

"I realise how completely applied African Research is, how outputs are targeted specifically at smallholder farmers and how much engagement goes on between scientists and farmers"

- Anne Edwards (JIC)

"I have learned which species have more importance and the main concerns and interest of the African researchers"

- Silvia Busoms (Nottingham University)

"In future collaborations, it is vital to understand the factors (social, cultural, technical) that will impact on the project whether positive or negative. It is important to understand what they perceive as challenges and their appetite as well as capacity to tackle them."

- James Canham (JIC PIPS student)

To showcase ACACIA's activity in Africa,

Thereby increasing the success of future capacity building.

Throughout the summer school, thanks to two PIPS students James Canham and Danny Ward, the Twitter feed was updated every day with several posts showcasing the activities of each day. The twitter feed continually linked John Innes Centre and Pwani University to what was happening on the course. An article on the course was written by James Canham for the ACACIA website and Danny Ward wrote a blog about his experience at the workshop. The recognition that AfriPlantSci brought to Pwani University been nicely summarised at the highest level at Pwani University:

"As Pwani University we are grateful to have been selected as the venue for the AfriPlantSci Summer School. The training created awareness, enhanced capacity, created an opportunity for researchers to network, brought forth new research ideas and opportunities for south south and north south collaborative research on African Plant Health. The experience gathered from the Summer School will have a lasting impact on African Plant Health Research in Pwani University, Kenya and Africa. As an institution we will strive to strengthen our partnership with John Innes Centre and continue to support AfriPlantSci activities"

- Pwani University Vice-Chancellor, Professor Mohamed S. Rajab.

AfriPlantSci 19 – A Summer School Making a Difference

"The training created awareness, enhanced capacity, created an opportunity for researchers to network, brought forth new research ideas and opportunities for south south and north south collaborative research on African Plant Health."

- Professor Mohamed S. Rajab, Vice-Chancellor, Pwani University.

Take a group of highly motivated, early-career African plant health researchers, an enthusiastic,

In summary

This second AfriPlantSci course exceeded my expectations on many fronts.

The participants were highly motivated, skilled and willing to learn. Pwani University were an excellent host and it was a pleasure working with them to deliver the course. And thank you to all the other organisers and trainers, including the PIPS, everyone was fully engaged, enthusiastic and open to the experience.

The course set a strong foundation for future events, collaborations and friendships which I am sure we will see come to fruition in the near future.

Tilly Eldridge

Course organiser, John Innes Centre.

Appendix

- Timetable (Appendix A)
- List of participants and trainers (with country and institution). (Appendix B)
- Theory of Change (Appendix C)

Appendix A

Timetable as it appeared in the course booklet

	3 rd April	4 th April	5 th April	6 th April	7 th April	
	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday	
7:00		Pwani Breakfast (LY)			Free time to work on concept note	
8:00	Transfer to Pwani					
8:30	Welcome, Introductions and Icebreaker (SdV, CD, Team)	Workshop 1a: Purpose Road Map (RK)	Scientific talk (LY)	Workshop 4: Critical Review (PIPs)		
9:00			Practical 1: DNA/RNA extraction (basic skills top up) (AE, TE, SBr & PIPs)			Theory 1: Salt stress/drought stress (SBu)
9:30		Workshop 3: presenting your research (PE)		Practical 2 Brainstorming on 3 adaptations (SBu)		
10:00						Workshop 1a: Purpose Road Map (RK)
10:30						
11:00						
11:30						
12:00						
12:30-13:30	Lunch					
13:30	Workshop 1a: Formulating your scientific question (proposals) (LY)	Workshop 3: presenting your research (PE)	Scientific talk (SdV)	Practical 2: Experimental designs to test plant adaptations (SBu)		Excursion
14:00			Practical 1 intro (AE & TE)			
14:30		Workshop 1b: proposals (LY)				
15:00	Practical 1 wrap up (team)					
15:30						
16:00						
16:30						
17:00-17:30						
17:30 - 18:00	Transfer to Mnarani Club					
18:00- 19:00	Self-reflection on the activities of the day					
19:00	Dinner at Mnarani Club			Dinner at boat yard	Dinner at Mnarani Club	
20:00	Informal reception with team (CD)	peer-coaching for concept note	Informal reception with LY & SB	peer-coaching for concept note	Free time	

Appendix A

Timetable as it appeared in the course booklet

	1 st April	2 nd April	3 rd April	4 th April	5 th April	6 th April	7 th April			
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday			
7:00		Pwani Breakfast (BW&CU)		Pwani Breakfast (WH)	Pwani Breakfast (DS)					
8:00	Transfer to Pwani									
8:30	Presentation intro Presenter BW,1,2	Presentation intro Presenter 3,4,5	Presentation intro Presenter 6,7,8	Presentation intro Presenter 9,10,11	Presentation intro Presenter 12,13,14					
9:00						Presentation intro Presenter 15,16,17				
9:30	AWARD	Wheat Genomics (CU)	Theory 2: CRISPR for crops	Journal club on GM and genome editing regulation (WH)	Theory 3: Field pathogenomics (DS)	Practical 5b: Bioinformatics for Field Pathogenomics (DS)				
10:00										
10:30		Workshop 5c: scientist core skills (CU & BW)	Practical 3 Creating stable transgenic plants (WH)	Practical 4a: Molecular analysis of GM and gene edited plants (PCR-based)	Journal club (DS)					
11:00										
11:30										
12:00										
12:30-13:30	Lunch									
13:30	Workshop 5b: scientist core skills (CU & BW)	Workshop 5d: scientist core skills (CU & BW)	Practical 3: Transient expression in a) <i>Nicotiana benthamiana</i> b) silico construct assembly	13:30 - 17:30 Practical 4: designing CRISPR constructs (WH) 14:30 - 15:30 Some Students to run gels to visualise PCR products	Practical 5a: Bioinformatics for Field Pathogenomics (DS)	Practical 5c: Bioinformatics for Field Pathogenomics (DS)				
14:00										
14:30										
15:00										
15:30										
16:00										
16:30	Speed cloning & breeding (BW)	LinkedIn Account Set Up (PIPS)	Transfer to dhow boat station							
17:00-17:30										
17:30 - 18:00	Transfer to Mnarani Club		Transfer to dhow boat station	Transfer to Mnarani Club						
18:00- 19:00	Self-reflection on the activities of the day			Self-reflection on the activities of the day						
19:00	Dinner at Mnarani Club					Dinner on beach- Mnarani				
20:00	Informal reception with CU & BW	peer-coaching for concept note	Free time	Biomakers challenge (PIPs)	Informal reception with DS	peer-coaching for concept note				

Free

Appendix A

Timetable as it appeared in the course booklet

	15 th April	16 th April
	Monday	Tuesday
7:00		Pwani Breakfast (SH)
8:00	Transfer to Pwani	
8:30	Presenter 18,19,20	Practical 8 Intro (SH)
9:00		Practical 7: genome based insect identification (SH)
9:30	Theory 4: Insect mediated plant disease (SH)	
10:00		
10:30	Journal club (SH)	
11:00		
11:30	Practical 6 intro (SH)	
12:00		
12:30-13:30	Lunch	
13:30	Practical 6: Insect mediated disease (SH)	Present finalized concept note (team)
14:00		
14:30		
15:00		Action plans and feedback (team)
15:30		
16:00		
16:30		
17:00-17:30		
17:30 - 18:00	Transfer to Mnarani Club	
18:00- 19:00	Self-reflection	
19:00	Dinner at Mnarani Club	
20:00	Informal reception with SH	Farewell mixer

Colour key

- Core skills workshop
- Research practical
- Lectures
- Networking
- Other

Initial key			
AE	Anne Edwards (JIC)	TE	Tilly Eldridge (JIC / Beca)
CD	Chris Darby (JIC)	BS	Burkhard Steurnagel (JIC)
LY	Levi Yant	BW	Brande Wulff (JIC)
PE	Peter Emmrich (JIC/ Beca)	CU	Cristobal Uauy (JIC)
PIPS	Isabel, Summer, Connor, Danny, Hans & James	DS	Diane Saunders (JIC)
RK	Rose Kigathi	RW	Roland Wouters (JIC)
SBr	Sian Bray (JIC)	SH	Saskia Hogenhout (JIC)
SBU	Silvia Busoms (JIC)	WH	Wendy Harwood (JIC)
SdV	Santie De Villiers (Pwani)	YM	Yvie Morgan (JIC)

Appendix B

Participants

Name	Institute	Country
Asibe, Flora Adachi	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan	NIGERIA
Gmakouba Tighankoumi	Togolese Agricultural Research Institute(ITRA)	Togo
Sodedji Kpedetin Ariel Frejus	University of Abomey-calavi	Benin
Kwabena Darkwa	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IIT); University of Ibadan	Nigeria
Nana Kofi Abaka Amoah	Africa Rice Center	Cote D'Ivoire
Edith Mugehu	Zimbabwe Sugar Association Experiment Station	Zimbabwe
Norman Muzhinji	University of Pretoria	South Africa
Borniface Juma Awalla	Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO)	Kenya
Elias Kibiwot Mibei	Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology	Kenya
David Livingstone Nsibo	University of Pretoria	South Africa
Janet Kimunye	International institute of Tropical Agriculture	Uganda
Ravelomanantsoa Santatra Herilalaina	National Research Centre of Applied Research for rural development - FOFIFA	Madagascar
Florence Munguti	KENYA PLANT HEALTH INSPECTORATE SERVICE (KEPHIS)	KENYA
Alimatu Sadia Osuman Haija	Crops Research Institute, Ghana	Ghana
Netsanet Bacha	Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (AWARD fellow)	Ethiopia
Biriah Ndiso	Pwani University	Kenya
Elisha Gogo	Pwani University	Kenya
Mounde Lenard	Pwani University	Kenya
Virginia Gichuru	Pwani University	Kenya
Wilton Mdinda	Pwani University	Kenya
Bahati Abdalla	Pwani University	Kenya
Eric Korir	National Biosafety Authority	Kenya

Appendix B

Trainers

Name	Institute	Country
Anne Edwards	JIC	Practicals Co-ordinator
Tilly Eldridge	JIC	Workshop Co-ordinator
Santie deVilliers	PU	Workshop Co-ordinator
Rose Kigathi	PU	Workshop Co-ordinator
Danny Ward	JIC	PIPS
Hans Pfalzgraf	UEA	PIPS
Isabel Diez-Santos	JIC	PIPS
Summer Rosonovski	UEA	PIPS
Connor Tansley	UEA	PIPS
James Canham	JIC	PIPS
Chris Darby	JIC	Director of Policy and International
Angela Payne	JIC	Workshop Administrator
Matt Heaton	JIC	Impact assessment and communications
Levi Yant	University of Nottingham	Trainer
Peter Emmrich	JIC	Trainer
Sian Bray	JIC	Trainer
Silvia Busoms	JIC/University of Nottingham	Trainer
Namumbya Monica Kapiriri	AWARD	Trainer
Cristobal Uauy	JIC	Trainer
Brandt Wulff	JIC	Trainer
Wendy Harwood	JIC	Trainer
Diane Saunders	JIC	Trainer
Burkhard Steurnagel	JIC	Trainer
Saskia Hogenhout	JIC	Trainer
Roland Wouters	JIC	Trainer

Appendix C
Theory of change

AfriPlantSci 2019 Thematic Framework

